

Synthesis of 2,5-disubstituted 1,3,4-oxadiazoles as potential antimicrobial agents

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Manuscript received 17 May 2004, revised 14 February 2005, accepted 13 April 2005

Several 2-(*N*-aryl carboxamido methyl thio)-5-[4-(styryl methine) amino phenyl]-1,3,4-oxadiazoles have been synthesized and tested for their antibacterial activities¹. Here we report the synthesis of 2,5-disubstituted 1,3,4-oxadiazoles by the following procedure.

p-Amino benzoyl hydrazine (**1**) of benzocaine was prepared by the treatment of hydrazine hydrate in ethanol. It was converted into 5-[4-amino phenyl]-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione (**2**) by refluxing with CS₂ in alcoholic solution of potassium hydroxide. **2** was converted into 5-[styryl methine]amino phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione (**3**) by refluxing with cinnamic aldehyde in ethanol. **3** was converted into 2-(*N*-phenyl carboxamido methyl thio)-5-[4-(styryl methine)aminophenyl]-1,3,4-oxadiazole (**4**) a title compound by treating with different *N*-chloro acetylated amines (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Characterization method : All the compounds synthesized were obtained in high purity by TLC using silica gel adsorbent and iodine as visualizing agent. The structure of the compounds was routinely checked by IR (KBr) scanned on Perkin-Elmer-157 and PMR spectra on Varian A60-D (using TMS standard) spectrophotometers respectively. The melting points reported were recorded in open capillaries and are uncorrected.

Antibacterial evaluation : The bacteria used were representatives of pathogenic bacteria from gram +ve groups and

gram -ve groups as well as rod shaped and coccaishaped bacterial group, i.e. *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. The study has been conducted according to the method adopted by Cruickshank *et al.*². Screening results show that the compounds were of moderate antibacterial level irrespective of the change in position of functional groups.

Experimental

Preparation of *p*-amino benzoyl hydrazine : Benzocaine was refluxed with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol in molar proportion to get corresponding hydrazide. (C₇H₉N₃O) m.p. 210°C (reported 208–211°C).

Preparation of 5-(4-amino phenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione : *p*-Amino benzoyl hydrazine (0.1 M) was added to the aqueous solution of KOH (0.1 M) with stirring followed by drop wise addition of methanol (100 ml) and then of CS₂ (0.1 M). The resulting solution was refluxed for 6 h, the solvent distilled off. The residue after dilution with water, filtered and the filtrate neutralized with acetic acid and the product worked up. (C₈H₇ON₃S; m.p. 259°C) (analysis : expt. N, 21.70, calcd. 21.76%).

Preparation of 5-[4-(styryl methine)amino]phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione : **2** (0.1 M) was dissolved in rectified spirit (75 ml) and to it cinnamic aldehyde (0.1 M) added drop wise. The content refluxed for 5 h, solvent distilled off and allowed to cool. The separated product filtered, washed with cold water and recrystallized from ethanol (C₁₇H₁₃ON₃S; m.p. 204°C; mol. wt. 307; analysis for nitrogen : obsd. 13.50; calcd. 13.68%).

Preparation of 2-(*N*-aryl carboxamide methyl thio)-5-[4-(styryl methine) amino phenyl]-1,3,4-oxadiazol : In a RBF **3** (0.01 M) was dissolved in aqueous KOH (25%). The reaction mixture heated to 80°C and chloro acetanilide

Note

Table 1. (*N*-Aryl carboxamido methylthio)-5-(4-(styryl methine)amino phenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole

Sl. no.	Ar =	Molecular formula	Molecular weight	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Carbon (%)	Hydrogen (%)	Nitrogen (%)	Antibacterial screening (mm)	
									<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₄ S	440.0	40	215.0	68.18	4.51	12.66	10	7
2.	-2(NO ₂)C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₅ S	485.0	48	82.0	61.76	3.90	14.24	16	12
3.	-4[CH(CH ₃) ₂]C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₄ S	482.0	46	72.0	69.68	5.32	11.32	22	11
4.	-4(Cl)C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₄ S.Cl	474.5	52	108.0	63.20	3.59	11.78	11	11
5.	-4(CH ₃)C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₄ S	454.0	44	92.0	68.65	4.80	12.32	8	11
6.	-2(Cl)C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₄ S.Cl	474.5	63	136.0	63.11	3.99	11.60	13	11
7.	-2:4(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₄ S	469.0	58	75.0	69.06	5.08	11.72	9	11
8.	-4(OCH ₃)C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₄ S	470.0	66	65.0	66.34	4.64	11.88	10	9
9.	-4(NO ₂)C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₅ S	485.0	48	56.0	61.77	3.87	14.28	16	12
10.	-4(OC ₂ H ₅)C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₄ S	484.0	52	64.0	66.33	4.90	11.50	12	11
11.	-2(Cl)4(NO ₂)C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₅ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₄ S.Cl	505.5	62	69.0	59.22	3.50	11.04	22	14
12.	-2:6(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₄ S	469.0	61	74.0	69.02	5.05	10.98	11	6
13.	-3(Cl)C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₄ S.Cl	474.5	70	84.0	63.13	3.96	11.78	11	9
14.	-3(OCH ₃)C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₄ S	470.0	58	100.0	66.16	4.66	11.66	16	13
15.	-3(CH ₃)C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₄ S	454.0	49	79.0	68.67	4.80	12.22	22	18

Standard : Chloramphenicol. Inhibition zone 32 mm.

Inhibition zone in mm at concentration of 0.05 ml (10 µg/ml) against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*.

PMR : δ 9.69 (-NH proton), δ 6.8-7.2 (m, Ar-H), δ 2.55 (S-CH₂), δ 2.2 (-CH₂), δ 5.2 (2H, -CH=CH-).

IR : 1652 (C=N str. cyclic), 1183 (C-O-C str. cyclic), 750 (C-S linkage), 1413 (CH₂, benzylic), 3413 (-NH str. acetamido group), 3057 cm⁻¹ (-CH=CH-str).

(0.014 M) in ethanol (95%, 10 ml) was added with constant stirring followed by refluxed it for 2 h. Worked up the product (C₂₅H₂₀O₂N₄S; m.p. 215°C; mol. wt. 440; analysis for nitrogen obsd. 12.66; calcd. 12.72%). Other compounds of this series (cited in Table 1) were synthesized by the same procedure.

References

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